

Smart IoT sensors network for monitoring of Cultural Heritage Monuments

Maria Krommyda, Nikos Mitro, and Angelos Amditis

Institute of Communication and Computer Systems,
42, Patision Str., Athens, Greece
`maria.krommyda@iccs.gr, nikos.mitro@iccs.gr, angelos.amditis@iccs.gr`
WWW home page: <https://i-sense.iccs.gr>

Abstract. The building materials of Cultural Heritage monuments are subjected to continuous degradation throughout the years, mainly due to their exposure to harsh and unexpected weather phenomena related to the Climate Change. The specific climatic conditions at their vicinity, especially when there are local peculiarities such as onshore breeze, are of crucial importance for studying the deterioration rate and the identification of proper mitigation actions. Generalized models that are based on climate data can provide an insight on the deterioration but fail to offer a deeper understanding of this phenomenon. To this end, in the context of the EU funded HYPERION project a distributed smart sensor network will be deployed at the Cultural Heritage monuments in four study areas as the solution to this problem. The platform includes smart IoT devices designed to provide environmental measurements close to monuments, a middle-ware to facilitate the communication and a visualization platform where the collected information is presented.

Keywords: Cultural Heritage, monument deterioration, IoT network, environmental monitoring, micro-climate sensors, IoT visualization

1 Introduction

Cultural Heritage (CH) sites and monuments are highly impacted by the Climate Change (CC) and related hazards, such as landslides. Deterioration of these monuments may cause significant adverse impacts on economies, politics and societies to the historical areas around them [3, 4]. The deterioration of CH sites is one of the biggest challenges in conservation. Aspects such as building technologies and materials, structural responses, preventive measures and restoration strategies, resilience and adaptation methodologies should be included in analysis. Currently there is no specific process towards understanding and quantifying CC effects on historic areas or assessing quantitatively and qualitatively the impact of various climatic parameters on the CH sites. In order to better study the phenomenon of the deterioration patterns of building materials there is a need to identify the various building materials at study areas and study their physical and mechanical characterisation [1]. Next, recession models should be

enriched with critical factors, which have not been studied so far, related to the micro-climate of the area. HYPERION [2] aims to support the development of such models by utilizing IoT network devices, called *smart tags* which will be installed within four historic study area. The IoT sensor network is based on small, autonomous, unattended, reliable and long life wireless devices that are deployed in certain selected part of the CH site that will continuously monitor for environmental changes. The collected measurements will be used to improve a number of dynamical and statistical models that will provide climate and environmental change information to extract quantified risk information for the CH areas. In this paper the distributed smart sensor network that will be deployed at the Cultural Heritage monuments in the four pilot cities are described. The network includes multiple smart tags that record specific measurement, based on the needed of the models, at the proximity of the Cultural Heritage monuments with different orientations aiming to provide the data needed for the study of the material degradation due to the climate conditions.

2 Sensor Design

Smart tags are edge network devices, equipped with environmental sensors, that are installed in certain buildings of the Cultural Heritage (CH) site. The smart tags are responsible for monitoring the environmental conditions and changes in the vicinity of the building walls, by acquiring accurate air temperature and humidity measurements. The tags also calculate the dew point temperature and monitor the dry/wet condition of the building walls. The smart tags are designed according to the needs of the pilot areas, taking into consideration the lack of infrastructure such as power and/or connectivity, in order to provide a reliable solution that is power efficient and weather resilient. As a result, a distributed network of autonomous, unattended, reliable and long life wireless tags, deployed in the interior/exterior walls of the buildings, is demonstrated. Based on these needs the functionalities provided by them are presented in Table 1.

The process flow diagram of the smart tags operation during a day is outlined in Figure 1. In detail, first the connected sensors to the microcontroller unit (MCU) are initialized. Then, measurements of the air temperature and humidity are acquired and stored in the flash memory using the SPI Flash Filing System (SPIFFS). The size of data that can be stored are up to 1.5Mbytes. Next, the dew point is calculated and the dry/wet condition is determined based on the resistance of the dew point sensor. These data are also stored on the flash memory. When all the new environmental data have been stored, the MCU goes into deep sleep mode for 30 minutes to achieve very low power consumption. During the deep sleep mode, the CPU and all the digital peripherals, including the WiFi and Bluetooth module, are shut down and only the ULP co-processor and RTC memory and peripherals are powered on. After 30 minutes the MCU wakes up from deep sleep and repeats the process of taking new measurements and store them. When 24 hours have passed, the stored data are formatted into JSON files. The MCU establish a network connection and publish the JSONs to the

Table 1. The functionalities provided by the smart tags.

Functionality	Description
Temperature and humidity measurements and dew point calculation	Record on a frequent basis (every 30 minutes) the air temperature and humidity and calculate the dew point temperature in the vicinity of the building walls.
Dry/Wet condition	Record on a frequent basis (every 30 minutes) the dry/wet condition of wall surfaces.
Data storage formatting and forwarding	Forward the measured data to the middleware on a daily basis, providing a daily time series of the data in JSON format.
Edge processing capabilities	Provide edge processing capabilities to push notifications to the middleware when the collected measurements are outside pre-defines, pilot-specific thresholds.
Low-power mode	Microcontroller operates on a low-power mode (deep sleep) most of the time to reduce power consumption to some μA and wake up only to measure or publish data.
Power management capability	The smart tag is powered by a rechargeable battery and a solar panel to ensure that they will meet the requirements for autonomy and long operational life. External power source via micro-USB is also possible.

middleware via MQTT protocol [5]. Once the data are published successfully, the flash memory with stored data is cleared and the chip goes into deep sleep again for the next 30 minutes. The firmware of the Smart Tags, that executes all the above operations, was implemented using the Arduino IDE. Their functionality can be extended as they can be reprogrammed by a micro-USB port.

The smart tag includes an ESP32 microcontroller [6], which is the main processing unit and hosts the sensors, and a Raspberry Pi Zero that is functioning as a data logger and gateway. The sensors connected to the smart tag are the Sensirion-SHTC3 and the SAMYOUNG SY-DS-1L [8]. Both sensors have been evaluated and they record reliable measurements with high sensitivity. The Sensirion-SHTC3 provides air temperature and relative humidity measurements and has low power consumption. The SAMYOUNG SY-DS-1L is used to determine the wet/dry condition on the building walls. The system architecture is also shown in Figure 2. The smart tags connect to the Raspberry Pi access point, which is connected to the network, over WiFi and publish the data via pub/sub MQTT protocol to the backend. The smart tags are powered based on a power management module, that include a rechargeable battery and a solar panel, to ensure that they meet the requirements for autonomy and long operational life. External power source via micro-USB is also supported to ensure smart tag operation.

ESP32 Microcontroller. The ESP32, shown in Figure 3, is the main processing unit of the smart tags that controls all its functions. It a low cost solution

Fig. 1. The process flow diagram of the smart tags

Fig. 2. System Architecture

that includes a powerful Xtensa 32-bit LX6 Dual-core processor, it has sufficient memory, it supports WiFi and Bluetooth connection and it can be configured to be low powered. Specifications:

- Xtensa 32-bit LX6 Dual-core processor and Ultra low power co-processor
- WiFi (2.4 GHz -2.5 GHz), Bluetooth 4.1 – BLE
- 448 KB ROM, 520 KB SRAM, 16 KB SRAM in RTC
- Current Consumption: WiFi Tx packet: 160-260mA, Idle mode: 30mA, Deep-Sleep: $10\mu A$
- Operating temperature : $-40^{\circ}C$ to $+85^{\circ}C$

Sensirion-SHTC3. Sensirion-SHTC3, shown in Figure 3, is a low cost, digital sensor that measures the temperature and relative humidity with high accuracy. The chip is consisted of a capacitive humidity sensor, a bandgap temperature sensor, analog and digital signal processing, A/D converter and calibration data memory. The communication with the ESP32 is managed with the digital, fast communication interface I2C. SHTC3 has also the capability to be set into a low power mode when it is not used. Specifications:

- Temperature: -40 to $+125^{\circ}C \pm 0.2^{\circ}C$
- Humidity: 0 - 100% $\pm 2.0\% RH$
- Current Consumption: Measurement (Low power mode): $270 - 570\mu A$, Sleep mode: $0.3 - 0.6\mu A$, Average (one measurement per second): $0.5\mu A$

SAMYOUNG SY-DS-1L. SAMYOUNG SY-DS-1L, shown in Figure 3, is a resistive analog dew sensor with resistivity that increases exponentially with relative humidity. The dry/wet condition of the walls can be determined based on the increase of sensor's resistivity. If the resistivity is increased exponentially the

Fig. 3. Smart Tag components

Fig. 4. Smart tag wire up schematic

condition is wet, otherwise it is dry. The threshold is determined based on sensor characteristics. The communication with the ESP32 is established via the ADC port to convert the analog value of the sensor into a digital measured value using firmware. Specifications:

- Humidity: 0 - 100% RH
- Current consumption: $20\mu A$
- Standard characteristics: $10k\Omega$ Max. at 80% RH, $100k\Omega$ Max. at 93% RH, $200k\Omega$ Max. at 88

Power management unit. The power management unit consists of a rechargeable Li-Ion 18650 3000mAh battery, a 6V-1.2W solar panel, a TP4056, shown in Figure 3, charging module responsible for the battery protection and the charging of the battery using the solar power, and last a voltage regulator that powers the ESP32 with steady voltage 3.3V from the battery. With a 3000mAh battery the smart tag can operate for about 6 months without sunlight. Using the solar energy to recharged the battery, the operational life of the smart tag can be further extended. Specifications:

- Voltage Supply: 4.5 to 5.5 V
- Battery protection
- Output charging current: 1A adjustable
- Output voltage: 3.7 - 4.2V
- Charge precision: 2%

Hardware assembly. The Smart tag wire up schematic is presented in Figure 4, which includes the following components:

- The ESP32 microcontroller and main processing unit.
- The Sensirion-SHTC3 temperature and relative humidity sensor.
- The SAMYOUNG SY-DS-1L dew sensor for wet/dry condition.
- The TP4056 charging module.

Fig. 5. Smart Tag Case

Fig. 6. Case Schematic/Dimensions

- The Li-Ion rechargeable 19650 3000mAh battery.
- The 6V 1.2W solar panel.
- The 100k resistor for the dew sensor.
- The MCP1700-3302E voltage regulator
- The 100nF ceramic capacitor and the 100 μ F electrolyte capacitor

Case. The smart tag case is designed using the Autodesk Fusion 360 software and printed by a 3D printer. It is constructed using ABS filament and it has IP56 rating, which means that it is waterproof and suitable for the required environmental conditions. The case is designed to be a compact element that contains the board, the battery and the solar panel in the exterior. The color is white in order to absorb as little as possible heat. There are also, small openings on the front and on the sides of the case to enable air circulation through the sensors and allow reliable measurements. The case design is shown in Figure 5, while its dimensions are shown in Figure 6.

3 Visualization Platform

The main purpose of the Smart Tag is to inform the end-users about the micro-climate in the vicinity of the installation points and provide them the ability to monitor live weather conditions and changes. In order to achieve that, a user-friendly visualization platform has been implemented that provides all the data measured by the Smart Tag.

Communication Protocol As already discussed, the acquired measurements are stored in Smart Tag’s flash memory and then published to the server at a daily basis. The communication protocol used for the data transmission is the MQTT messaging protocol. MQTT is a publish/subscribe network protocol that provides bi-directional connections between devices. The MQTT protocol has been chosen over other protocols e.g HTTP, because it is a lightweight solution that requires minimal network bandwidth and achieve faster throughput. Furthermore, it offers lower complexity with basic functionalities such as connect, publish, subscribe, disconnect and transfers data as a byte array, which is it perfect for resource-constrained devices like Smart Tag. A Mosquitto MQTT broker is installed on a Raspberry Pi Zero gateway, where the data are gathered and processed. The Mosquitto broker was chosen because it is open-source, lightweight and easily deployed.

Fig. 7. Node-RED flow for the user interface

Fig. 8. User interface

User Interface The interface is designed to present all measured data in a precise, user-friendly and simple developed way. For that purpose, the Node-RED framework is installed and used on the Raspberry Pi. Node-RED is an open source programming tool for developing application interfaces and online services. It provides a browser-based visual programming interface that allows the developer to use and connect nodes, instead of writing code and as a result it reduces the complexity of the development. Each node execute a process and all the nodes wired together form a flow, which is the whole program. The flow of the Smart Tag’s UI is composed of a MQTT input node that receives the measurements from the Smart Tag, a JSON parser, a node that process the data and the output nodes that visualize each measurement. The designed flow is outlined in Figure 7.

The Node-RED dashboard is a module that provide specific nodes for the live visualization of the data. The designed dashboard is composed of temperature, humidity and dew point gauges with the lives measurements, temperature and humidity charts that visualize all measured data during a day and the Dry/Wet state of the walls. The UI is presented in the Figure 8.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we present the development of smart IoT devices that monitor specific environmental conditions in the vicinity of cultural heritage buildings. These IoT devices, are designed to be autonomous, power efficient and deployable with a non intrusive way on the buildings walls. Further-more, a visualization platform is designed to present the measurements in a user friendly way. It is mentioned that Smart Tag’s functionality is limited on a sensor-monitor level and it is not suitable to operate as a data processing device that executes computations with high complexity, because of its constrained resources (e.g memory, power consumption). The data acquired by the Smart Tags can be further processed on the server’s back-end side and can be used for modelling or simulation purposes.

Acknowledgment

This work is a part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (Horizon 2020) under grant agreement no. 821054. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

References

1. Shabani A, Kioumarsis M, Plevris V, Stamatopoulos H. Structural Vulnerability Assessment of Heritage Timber Buildings: A Methodological Proposal. *Forests*. 2020; 11(8):881. doi:10.3390/f11080881
2. HYPERION Project, <https://www.hyperion-project.eu/>
3. Cassar, M. and Pender, R. (2005) The impact of climate change on cultural heritage: evidence and response. In: Verger, I., (ed.) 14th Triennial Meeting, The Hague, 12-16 September 2005. Preprints (Volume 2). James & James, London, pp. 610-616. ISBN 9781844072538.
4. Hambrecht, G., & Rockman, M. (2017). International approaches to climate change and cultural heritage. *American Antiquity*, 82(4), 627-641. doi:10.1017/aaq.2017.30
5. Singh, M., Rajan, M. A., Shivraj, V. L., & Balamuralidhar, P. (2015, April). Secure MQTT for Internet of Things (IoT). In 2015 fifth International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (pp. 746-751). IEEE. doi:10.1109/CSNT.2015.16.
6. Maier, A., Sharp, A., & Vagapov, Y. (2017, September). Comparative analysis and practical implementation of the ESP32 microcontroller module for the internet of things. In 2017 Internet Technologies and Applications (ITA) (pp. 143-148). IEEE. doi:10.1177/0020294019857748
7. Sensirion-SHTC3. https://www.sensirion.com/fileadmin/user_upload/customers/sensirion/Dokumente/2_Humidity_Sensors/Datasheets/Sensirion_Humidity_Sensors_SHTC3_Datasheet.pdf
8. SAMYOUNG-SY-DS-1L. <http://samyoungsnc.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Datasheet--SY-DS-1-Series-Ver.1.8-Standard.pdf>